

SKIN EFFECT: A NATURAL PHENOMENON FOR MINIMIZATION OF GROUND BOUNCE IN VLSI RC INTERCONNECT

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Abstract : As the frequency of operation has attained a range of GHz and signal rise time continues to increase interconnect technology is suffering due to various high frequency effects as well as ground bounce problem. In some recent studies a high frequency effect i.e. skin effect has been modeled and its drawbacks have been discussed. This paper strives to make an impression on the advantage side of modeling skin effect for interconnect line. The proposed method has considered a CMOS with RC interconnect. Delay and noise considering ground bounce problem and with skin effect are discussed. The simulation results reveal an advantage of considering skin effect for minimization of ground bounce problem during the working of the model. Noise and delay variations with temperature are also presented

Keywords : Interconnect, Skin effect, Ground Bounce, Delay, Noise.

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